

POLICY AND ORGANIZATIONAL ANALYSIS OF PANCASILA EDUCATION AND NATIONAL INSIGHT IN EAST KALIMANTAN

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ABSTRACT

In today's global era, the challenges and problems for national unity, integrity and sovereignty of the state are getting bigger. Strengthening the values of Pancasila and national insight in people's lives is very important. All levels of government, including the East Kalimantan regional government, have the duty and responsibility to maintain Pancasila and strengthen national insight. The issuance of Regional Regulation (Perda) Number 9 of 2023 concerning the Implementation of Pancasila Education and National Insight and several other government regulations are public policies related to this. This study aims to analyze the profile, context, and substance of policies and organizational dimensions in the regional regulation and various other relevant regulations. This study uses normative legal methods, and literature studies, by examining the substance of government regulations, local governments and analysis of various relevant documents. The results of the study indicate that Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023 is a public policy regarding the Pancasila ideology and national insight. Hierarchically, there are several state and government policies as references, including the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 71 of 2012 concerning Guidelines for National Insight Education. There are several aspects of policy in the regulation, namely policy objectives, policy substance, policy implementing organizations, policy targets, details of policy activities, and policy resources. Several regional officials, including elements of the military, police, political parties and social organizations are policy actors. In addition, there are several dimensions of the organization regulated in the regulation. The threat of the fading practice of Pancasila and national insight is a policy issue. The provincial government, DPRD, military organizations, police organizations and institutions outside the government that care about the issue of strengthening national insight are policy institutions. The hope that the Pancasila ideology will be stronger and national insight in society will be stronger is the policy environment. There are several policy substances in the regulation that need to be refined. Several organizational dimensions are present in these regulations. Several policy elements in these regulations require refinement.

Keywords : policy, organization, Pancasila education, national insight.

INTRODUCTION

In social, national, and state life, human integrity will significantly determine the future of the nation and state. Humans not only function as citizens who do not hold political power, but also as those who hold the reins of government. In this context, integrity must be interpreted as, among other things, commitment, loyalty, dedication, discipline, and responsibility as Indonesians towards the continuity of the Indonesian state. Therefore, it is not surprising that in the explanatory text of the 1945 Constitution before the 1999 amendment, it can be read that the most important thing in state administration is not the completeness of the constitution, but rather the enthusiasm of state administrators.

From another perspective, it can be said that the integrity or spirit of state administration is related to and stems from the character of individual Indonesians, which cumulatively reflects the character of the nation. This factor significantly determines the quality of the nation in question, including in state governance and national development. According to Lickona, character consists of operative values, values in action. Character, thus conceived, has three interrelated components: moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral behavior. Good character consists of knowing the good, desiring the good, and doing the good – habits of the mind, habits of the heart, and habits of action (1992:51). This national character, in the greater interests of the nation and state, is reflected in a national perspective that is philosophically aligned with the values embodied in the state's foundation and national ideology, Pancasila.

In this regard, the government's strategic efforts to intensify character education are crucial for the fate and future of the nation as a whole. The government, including regional governments, has a responsibility to implement various strategic steps to instill national insight rooted in Pancasila values in various components of society, so that the nation is increasingly prepared to compete in today's global era. Regarding education policy, the government has issued Presidential Regulation (Perpres) No. 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education. Furthermore, as an elaboration of Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, each regional government has also issued regional policies in the form of regional regulations and regional head regulations concerning the implementation of education, one of which is character education.

In East Kalimantan, Regional Regulation (Perda) No. 9 of 2023 concerning Pancasila Education and National Insight has been issued. Regional government regulations regarding national insight education, which also relate to character education, constitute public policy. Public policy is the combination of basic decisions,

commitments, and actions made by those who hold or influence government positions of authority (Gerston, 2010:7). In other words, it can be said that this is part of education policy, or public policy that covers the field of education. This is in line with Parson's statement that some of the key areas of public policy include health, transportation, education, and environmental and social policy..." (1997:31). One of the substantive areas of this public policy is education, specifically character education, Pancasila education, and national insight education. These regulations constitute public policy because they are established by state/government institutions to address public issues, particularly those related to the challenges and obstacles faced by today's young generation.

This research aims to analyze the policy content as an element of the Policy System, from the perspective of its profile, hierarchy, and context. It also analyzes the organizational dimensions stipulated in East Kalimantan Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023, as well as various other relevant laws and regulations concerning national insight education.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research combines normative juridical methods with literature and documentation studies. Based on its level of explanation, this research is classified as descriptive research, one type of which is library and documentary research. This normative juridical method is a type of research in the field of legal science, normative legal research, or library law, conducted through the examination of library materials or secondary data. The research is conducted on information documented in the form of regulations, thus commonly known as document analysis or content analysis.

In detail, the focus of the study is East Kalimantan Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023 and the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation (Permendagri) Number 71 of 2012 concerning . In addition, all state and government regulations related to it, namely Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, Presidential Regulation (Perpres) Number 87 of 2017, and Government Regulation (PP) Number 38 of 2007 concerning the Division of Government Affairs Between the Government, Provincial Regional Governments, and Regency/City Regional Governments. Permendikbud Number 23 of 2015 concerning the Development of Character, and Permendikbud Number 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education in Formal Education Units.

Various non-human data sources, such as documents, photographs, and statistical materials, can be viewed as sources that can be used to find answers to research questions. All of these relate to documents that are substantively related to the Pancasila and national insight education policies or programs in East Kalimantan Province. The technique used to analyze secondary data is content analysis. This analysis is used to obtain information from all forms of communication delivered in symbolic form, including letters, regulations, and laws. These are then classified, reviewed, and interpreted to draw conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile, Hierarchy, and Context of National Insight Policy

East Kalimantan Provincial Regulation Number 9 of 2023, enacted on November 29, 2023, consists of 18 articles and is an operational policy that refers to the provisions of Article 3 of Home Affairs Regulation Number 71 of 2012. A very long time span elapsed between the issuance of this regulation and the issuance of the regulation, namely 11 years. In fact, the policy on national insight education is fundamental to maintaining the integrity of the state and national unity. Hierarchically, several other state policies that serve as the legal basis for this regulation include Law No. 12 of 2011 concerning the Formation of Legislation, Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, and Home Affairs Ministerial Regulation No. 80 of 2015 concerning the Formation of Regional Legal Products. The context of national insight education is not only reflected in the title of the regional regulation, but also in the considerations of letter b, the objectives of national insight education in Article 2, and the material for national insight education in Article 4.

As a legal reference for all regional governments in issuing regional regulations on national insight education, Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 71 of 2012 consists of 22 articles and was enacted on October 29, 2012. This policy product established by the Minister of Home Affairs is based, among other things, on Law Number 32 of 2014, and Government Regulation Number 38 of 2007 concerning the Division of Government Affairs between the Central Government, Provincial Governments, and Regency/City Governments. The context of national insight education is evident in Article 3 Paragraph (2) concerning the objectives of national insight education, Article 4 concerning policy targets, Article 5 concerning policy approaches, and Article 7 concerning the content of national insight material.

Law Number 20 of 2003, enacted on July 8, 2003, consists of 77 articles, including those that declare Law Number 2 of 1989 concerning the National Education System

no longer valid. Its connection to national insight education, which is closely correlated with national character, is evident in the provisions of Article 1, number 1, concerning the definition of education, Article 3 concerning the function of national education, and Article 4 Paragraph (1) concerning the principles of education administration. Hierarchically, this law was issued based on five articles of the 1945 Constitution.

Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017, enacted on September 6, 2017, consists of 18 articles. The relationship of this presidential regulation to character education is illustrated, among other things, by the title of the presidential regulation and the consideration in letter b, which states that strengthening character education is necessary to realize a cultured nation. Hierarchically, Article 13 Paragraph (5) of the presidential regulation states, among other things, that each regional government is responsible for formulating policies and implementing action plans in accordance with its authority. Ministerial Regulation of Education and Culture Number 23 of 2015, consisting of 9 articles, was enacted on July 13, 2015, replacing Ministerial Regulation of Education and Culture Number 21 of 2015. The issuance of this regulation is based, among other things, on Law Number 20 of 2003 and Government Regulation Number 17 of 2003. Its context, related to national insight education and character education, is evident in the consideration of letter c, which states that character education should be a joint movement involving the central government, regional governments, the community, and/or parents.

The formulation of policies issued by the state in the form of laws and by central and regional government officials is part of what Dunn calls The Policy System (1981:86). This is a conceptual unity consisting of three elements: public policy, the policy environment, and policy stakeholders. The policy environment is characterized by the anxiety of some citizens regarding the diminishing sense of love and belonging to the nation and state, as demonstrated by the behavior of some other citizens. This manifests in various forms of behavior that violate the law and other social norms, including rampant corruption, drug crimes, online gambling, terrorism, environmental destruction, and the spread of slander, hoaxes, and hate speech. Government officials, both civil and military, in East Kalimantan, as well as various institutions and actors in society involved and interested in national insight education are policy stakeholders.

National Insight Policy Substance

From a public policy perspective, the inclusion of policy objectives in every government regulation, the substance of which concerns the public interest, is crucial and strategic. The six objectives of national insight education, as outlined in Article 2

of Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023, relate to national values, the performance of regional democracy, educational models that align with local wisdom and are not indoctrinating, the establishment of national insight education hubs, proposed policy changes, and collaborative networks with various parties. These policy objectives, in the legal basis for its formation, namely Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 71 of 2012, are stated in Article 3 Paragraph (2).

Conceptually, the existence of this policy objective aligns with Anderson's opinion that one characteristic of public policy is purposive or goal-oriented action, rather than random or chance behavior (1978:3). As something to be achieved in the future, the objective of this national insight policy aligns with its meaning and significance for the integrity of the nation and state. In Kurniawan's view, national insight provides individuals and society with the understanding to appreciate differences, strengthen a sense of unity, and maintain the stability and integrity of the nation. Furthermore, it plays a crucial role in building awareness of the values of democracy, human rights, social justice, and upholding the spirit of mutual cooperation and togetherness in carrying out community life (2023:138). The Indonesian national insight mandates that all citizens place unity, integrity, and the interests and safety of the nation and state above personal and group interests. Diversity and plurality should not be divisive, but rather a force that enriches unity (Sofyan and Dadang Sundawa, 2015:185).

Another important aspect in understanding the issuance of this national insight education policy is the background or considerations of the policymakers. This is evident in the consideration "Considering" letter a of Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 71 of 2012, which stipulates the obligation of regional governments to uphold Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution and to uphold and preserve the integrity of the state. Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023, in the consideration "Considering" letter b, states that the implementation of national insight education is to enhance the practice of Pancasila and foster harmony and tolerance within a diverse society. These two considerations demonstrate the commitment of the East Kalimantan government and regional government to maintaining the integrity of the nation and state. This aligns with Anderson's opinion that one of the values influencing decision-making related to the public interest is policy values (1978:14). From a public policy perspective, the relevance between national insight education and character education is very strong, as stipulated in the national education system regulated by Law Number 20 of 2003. At the very least, this is evident from the definition, basis, function, objectives, and principles of national education. National education, as referred to in Article 1 number 2, is education based on Pancasila and

the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, rooted in religious values, Indonesian national culture, and responsive to the demands of changing times. The mention of religious values and national culture as the roots of the basis of education demonstrates the commitment of policymakers to both aspects in character formation. This explicitly demonstrates the seriousness of the state's political stance on the importance of education for the future of the nation. In the view of Sofyan and Dadang Sundawa, the state is responsible for preparing a young generation with national insight and a strong spirit of nationalism in the life of the nation and state (2015:184). In other words, the growth of national insight and the maintenance of national integration are not things that can grow and develop in the blink of an eye, but must go through a long, systematic and consistent process, especially through the education process.

In accordance with the name of the policy, namely national insight education, the existence of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 71 of 2012 and Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023 is also inseparable from national education policy. The basis of national education as stated in Article 2 of Law Number 20 of 2003 is Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. This is also explicitly related to the estuary of the nation's character, especially the five fundamental values of the five principles of Pancasila as the philosophical foundation and essential values that are densely and comprehensively contained in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution. The function of national education as stated in Article 3 is to develop the ability and form the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to enlighten the life of the nation. Regarding the character emphasized in Law Number 20 of 2003, it appears in Article 6 Paragraph (1) letter a of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation that one approach in national insight education is the development of national character. Similarly, Article 4, letter c of Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023 outlines four types of national mental development, which essentially reflect the national character that is to be developed. These include anti-intolerance, anti-radicalism, and anti-terrorism education; anti-corruption education; anti-drug education; and anti-sexual violence and bullying education.

This formulation of the function of national education clearly and explicitly demonstrates its relevance to the national character that is to be built and developed through national education. National insight education, introduced in Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 71 of 2012 and Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023, clearly demonstrates a long-term policy for maintaining national integration. Therefore, according to Baedowi and Lilik Kartika Sari, strengthening national insight must be carried out continuously in line with the dynamics of national and state life.

Understanding national insight among the younger generation will have implications for the future existence of the state, the nation's progress, and the spirit of national and state life (2023:16028). Awareness of the importance of national insight will ensure the Indonesian nation retains its dignity and honor, as well as its existence and identity as a pluralistic, independent, and sovereign nation among the world's nations (Priyanto et al., 2023).

In line with its substance regarding education policy, the existence of Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 71 of 2012 and Regional Regulation No. 9 of 2023 is inseparable from the general goals of national education. Article 3 of Law No. 20 of 2003 states that the goal of national education is to develop the potential of students to become individuals who believe in and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens. These nine characteristics of Indonesians as students that are to be developed constitute the nation's character. In other words, this national character is what the issuance of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation and the regional regulation aims to build, as it relates to the nation's efforts to achieve its national goals. Habibah and Lutfiah Noer Anisa Raoyani stated that national insight can be interpreted as our perspective as an Indonesian nation towards the problems that exist in Indonesia by prioritizing unity and unity in national and state life to achieve the national goals of the Indonesian nation (2024:44).

National insight education cannot be carried out haphazardly, as it must comply with various general educational principles. As stated in Article 4 of Law Number 20 of 2003, education is organized based on several principles, including that education be conducted democratically and fairly and non-discriminatory, upholding human rights, religious values, cultural values, and national diversity. This also explicitly emphasizes the importance of character, which must be upheld in the implementation of education. In the view of Damanik et al., the strengthening and development of national insight must be continuously carried out in line with the ongoing process of life (2023:94). National integration education is required to prevent conflicts and national disintegration by teaching students integration values. Therefore, teachers play an essential role in national integration learning by instilling fundamental values such as respect, tolerance, and togetherness (Rahman et al., 2025:32).

In the context of national development oriented towards the interests of the nation and state in the future, national insight as part of the political development aspect must continue to be promoted to various elements of society. Soemaatmadja

stated that the national insight contains a commitment and a spirit of unity to ensure the existence and improvement of the quality of life of the nation and requires adequate knowledge of present and future challenges as well as various potentials of the nation (2020: 262). The importance and strategy of national insight as a national character is also mentioned in Law Number 17 of 2007 concerning the Long-Term Development Plan 2005-2025. In Appendix Number IV.1 of the Direction of Long-Term Development 2005-2025, it is stated, among other things, that the development and strengthening of national identity is aimed at realizing a national character and social system that is rooted, unique, modern and superior. This is understandable, because national development must be carried out not only as people-oriented development, but also people-centered development. In this regard, Aulia argues that national insight is essentially a view or point of view that reflects the attitude and personality of the Indonesian people who have a love for the country, uphold unity, and have a sense of togetherness as a nation to build Indonesia towards a better future, amidst competition (2020:203).

Regarding the national character aligned with the national insight as outlined in the two laws, Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 was subsequently issued. The Presidential Regulation's considerations state that strengthening character education is necessary to realize a cultured nation through strengthening the values of religiousness, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creativity, independence, democracy, curiosity, national spirit, love of the homeland, appreciation of achievement, communication, love of peace, a love of reading, environmental awareness, social awareness, and responsibility. Of these 19 character traits, at least six are directly related to national insight education: tolerance, democracy, national spirit, love of the homeland, environmental awareness, and social awareness.

The values of Pancasila imparted through the educational process in formal and non-formal educational institutions essentially reflect character education, namely the character of the Indonesian people that is in harmony with the nation's outlook on life that was initiated in 1945. One of the objectives of strengthening character education as stated in Article 2 of Presidential Decree Number 87 of 2017 is to build and equip students as the golden generation of Indonesia in 2045 with the spirit of Pancasila and good character education to face the dynamics of change in the future. In this regard, Malau et al. stated that having an understanding of national insight is something that is very important for all levels of Indonesian society, especially students. Nationalistic insight is one of the social values derived through an understanding of the ideological values contained in Pancasila (2024:31)

The substance of the Pancasila education policy and national insight is also related to identity as a nation that must be demonstrated with confidence in international relations. In the view of Gani et al., national identity is a means to unite and overcome existing differences, as well as a strong foundation for building collective awareness, solidarity, and a sense of belonging to the Indonesian nation (et al., 2023:172). The national identity and personality instilled in Pancasila education and national insight are also faced with increasing challenges and threats in the current digital era. Fatimah et al., stated that the negative impact of the flow of information from around the world in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 is in the form of a fading of national values, caused by a lack of love for the homeland among citizens, which is a threat to the life of the nation and state (2020:31). National integration is very important to raise awareness of the identity of the Indonesian state, strengthen national identity, and national unity (Ari et al., 2023:428). A deep understanding of the values of unity can be applied in various aspects of community life and will help strengthen a sense of togetherness and solidarity amidst the nation's plurality (Situmeang and Yakobus Ndona, 2024:156).

Organizational Dimensions of National Insight Policy

From an organizational theory perspective, the existence of organizational goals or program objectives is crucial, as they will guide all components and members of the organization in carrying out their duties in accordance with their authority. The affirmation of the six objectives of national insight education as stated in Article 2 of Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023 provides strong support for the effective achievement of these objectives. Similarly, the six objectives of implementing national insight education are stated in Article 3 Paragraph (2) of Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 71 of 2012. From an organizational conceptual perspective, these objectives, as stated by Siagian, are fundamental to administration, management, and organization (2008:5). These objectives are certainly related to the broader interests of the nation and state and have a futuristic dimension, as they will have implications for the existence and sustainability of the nation and state. Soemaatmadja stated that the nation's future is largely determined by national insight education. Collaboration with other stakeholders will strengthen the implementation of each party's respective duties in implementing national insight education (2020:113).

It is also appropriate to emphasize the implementation of Pancasila and national insight education, as stipulated in Article 6 paragraph (1) of Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023, which includes regional apparatuses that administer government affairs in the areas of national unity and politics, as well as in education

and culture. This aligns with Henry Fayol's concept of authority and responsibility as elements of the general principles of administration and organization (Robbins, 1990). This is reinforced by provisions in Article 15, including the Governor of East Kalimantan's duty to oversee the implementation of Pancasila and national insight education. From the perspective of administrative and organizational theory, this supervision is one of the organic functions of administration and management to observe and ensure that all ongoing organizational activities comply with established plans (Siagian, 2008:112). Likewise, explicit and imperative regulation of funding for Pancasila and national insight education, as stated in Article 17, is appropriate, given the crucial role of funding in the success of this policy. From an organizational and managerial perspective, funding or finance is one of the organization's most crucial resources for the effective achievement of goals (Ortigas, 1994:8; Silalahi, 2018:157).

Similarly, the affirmation in Article 13, Article 14, and Article 15 of Home Affairs Ministerial Regulation Number 71 of 2012 concerning the National Insight Education Center at the provincial and district/city levels, which must be established by the regional head, is appropriate and important. This organization is *ex officio* chaired by the Regional Secretary and is tasked with implementing national insight education, consisting of vertical agencies, regional government elements, and community elements. In organizational theory terminology, this can be said to be one of the five main elements of an organization that Henry Mintzberg called the operating core, namely the organizational unit that carries out the main tasks technically and operationally (Robbins, 1990). The existence of regulations regarding the requirement for consultation and coordination as mentioned in Article 16 is also appropriate. This relates to one of the structural dimensions of the organization as stated by Daft, namely the hierarchy of authority that describes who reports to whom and the span of control for each manager (1992:13). Also important for the successful achievement of organizational goals is the existence of regulations regarding evaluation activities. In Siagian's view, this evaluation is an activity to measure and compare actual work results with those that should be achieved (2008:317). This evaluation is especially urgent when it is clear that the challenges to national integration, or the potential for national disintegration, are significantly related to Indonesia's socio-cultural conditions. Hermawanto et al. state that national integration is a bond and togetherness among citizens without differentiation of ethnicity, religion, belief, or culture. This is a form of unity, brotherhood, and social cohesion within the community and society within a country. National integration helps keep the country united and strong from within, despite its pluralism (2023:278).

The position and role of national insight are central and absolutely necessary, serving as the spirit, soul, and spirit of the existence and dynamics of the nation and state (Martodirjo, 2008:3). Horizontal social differentiation and vertical social stratification, which are in fact an inseparable part of Indonesian society, must be interpreted with wisdom. In this regard, national integration based on the national insight inherent in every citizen must become a solid socio-political and socio-cultural fact. Hia stated that this diversity that Indonesia possesses can be a tremendous advantage if the community and government can utilize it well, but this diversity can also be a major threat to the country if nationalism is not implemented properly in society (2021:10384).

Collaboration between regional governments and various community components to ensure the success of Pancasila education and national insight is crucial. Therefore, the provisions of Article 7 of Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023, which regulates the existence of the Pancasila and National Insight Education Forum (P3WK Forum), will strengthen this policy, which is fundamental to the strength of national unity. This is evident in Article 7 Paragraph (3), which, among other things, mentions the involvement of community, social, and cultural organizations in the P3WK Forum. Siregar stated that a synergistic relationship between parents and teachers is crucial and necessary in shaping a young generation with a strong national insight and sense of nationalism (2022:265). Public participation and awareness in assuming responsibility for education are not merely hopes, but urgent demands that must be realized in concrete activities on the ground. This participation has existed for a long time, reflected in various forms and expressions in society (Khaliqa, 2017:17).

In the context of organizational theory, the provisions regarding the involvement of various community components in Pancasila and national insight education programs in Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023 demonstrate the responsiveness of government organizations to their organizational environment. According to Robbins, this environment is everything outside an organization. The specific environment is that part of the environment that is directly relevant to the organization in achieving its goals (1990:206). This is all the more crucial because without public support and participation, the government cannot optimally bear the burden of development. According to Kurniawan et al., community participation in various programs is significant because the community acts as a driving agent for socio-cultural change, transmitting the values of Pancasila and national insight in daily life and providing moral and spiritual support to socialize them to all elements of society (2022:165).

The establishment of regional apparatuses that, among others, handle aspects of national unity and politics, education and culture, as well as youth and sports in Article 6 of Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2023 is an affirmation of the importance of national integration that is to be instilled through the educational process. National integration is not a coercion that unites different cultures to be the same as others, but this national integration is the preservation of unity and the right to be self-determining, so the community as a determinant they want the differences to be the same as the others (Putri, et al., 2023: 112). Understanding the values of Pancasila is not only obtained through formal education, but also through education provided by parents and environmental influences. Misunderstanding the values of Pancasila is dangerous and threatens national unity (Novanda, et al., 2024: 8). If efforts are not made to strengthen national insight in the current era, the Indonesian nation will lose its identity and existence on the international stage (Purwantoro et al., 2023:58). National insight shapes orientation, perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors shared by all citizens. Its appreciation must be explored deeply, not merely through possessing enthusiasm and mastering national ideology (Wahyono, 2007:70).

CONCLUSION

National insight, rooted in the values of Pancasila, is highly strategic for the integration and future of the nation. The government, including the regional government of East Kalimantan, is required to seriously implement it through Pancasila education and national insight, which are closely linked to national character. State and regional government policies, particularly Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 71 of 2012 and Regional Regulation No. 9 of 2023, demonstrate a serious concern for national character. There is a hierarchical relationship between state and government policies, aligned with each other at each level of government. The Minister of Home Affairs Regulation and the regional regulation contain various aspects of public policy and organizational dimensions. Several policy elements in Regional Regulation No. 9 of 2023 require refinement.

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